

Report of the European Commission workshop on “The roadmap towards phasing out animal testing for chemical safety assessments”, Brussels, 11–12 December 2023

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ABSTRACT

This report summarises the main findings and discussion from the European Commission (EC) workshop on “The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments” which was held in Brussels on 11–12 December 2023. The aim of the workshop was to gather ideas and opinions from individuals, organisations and institutions, and to discuss potential approaches for incorporating non-animal methods into chemical legislation with all interested stakeholders. The roadmap will be an EC policy document which will outline milestones and specific actions, addressing all relevant pieces of chemical legislation relating to safety assessment. It intends to describe the necessary steps to replace animal testing in pieces of legislation where it is currently required for chemical safety assessments. The roadmap will outline the path to expand and accelerate the development, validation and implementation of non-animal methods as well as means to facilitate their uptake across legislation. The workshop included presentations from a wide variety of stakeholders. The contributors provided examples of how non-animal methods could be applied to replace, reduce or refine animal testing in the assessment of human health and environmental effects. Furthermore, possible guiding principles for establishing a Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) in European chemicals legislation were also discussed. The workshop provided the basis for further discussion and for structuring the roadmap work.

1. Introduction to, and purpose of, the workshop

1.1. Introduction to the workshop

This report presents the main findings from the European Commission (EC) workshop on “The Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments”. The workshop was a hybrid event held in Brussels and on-line over two days (11–12 December 2023). It was

attended by over 500 participants representing regulatory agencies, industry, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), projects and academia, as well as EU competent authorities and the European Commission.

The aim of the workshop was to identify the major challenges and potential solutions in moving towards animal-free chemical safety assessment and to inform the roadmap to achieve this goal. Specifically, the workshop provided an opportunity for broad stakeholder input and

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Abbreviations	
3Rs	Replacement, Reduction and Refinement
3RsWP	EMA Working Party on the 3Rs
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
APCRA	Accelerating the Pace of Chemical Risk Assessment
ASPA	ASPIS-initiated Safety Profiling Algorithm
ASPIS	Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies (collaboration of EU Horizon2020-funded projects ONTOX, PrecisionTox and RISK-HUNT3R)
C&L	Classification and Labelling
CLP	(Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 on) Classification, Labelling and Packaging
DA	Defined Approach
EBA	Exposure-Based Adaptation
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ECI	European Citizens' Initiative
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EPAA	European Partnership for Alternative Approaches to Animal Testing
ESA	Environmental Safety Assessment
ESEC	European Specialised Expert Community
EU	European Union
GD	Guidance Document
GHS	(UN) Globally Harmonized System (for classification and labelling of chemicals)
GLP	Good Laboratory Practice
HSI	Humane Society International
IATA	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment
ICCVAM	Interagency Coordinating Committee on the Validation of Alternative Methods
KE	Key Event
MAD	Mutual Acceptance of Data
NAM	Non-Animal Method/New Approach Methodology
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NGRA	Next-Generation Risk Assessment
NIVA	Norwegian Institute for Water Research
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OoC	Organ-on-a-Chip
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PBK	Physiologically-Based Kinetic
PoD	Point of Departure
qAOP	quantitative AOP
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
REACH	Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
SIR	Standard Information Requirement
TG	Test Guideline
TK	Toxicokinetics
TTC	Threshold of Toxicological Concern
UN	United Nations
US	United States
UVCB	(Substance of) Unknown or variable composition, complex reaction product(s) or of biological origin
WHO	World Health Organization
WoE	Weight of Evidence

allowed the exchange of ideas, which contribute to the roadmap. There was also an opportunity to establish closer links with external activities that can feed into the roadmap, e.g., European Union (EU) funded projects, stakeholder representations etc. As part of this process, the workshop also intended to allow critical reflection on the process of bringing Non-Animal Methods into regulatory frameworks and the changes required.

The workshop was opened by Ms Kristin Schreiber (Director, EC DG GROW) and Mrs Tilly Metz (Member of the European Parliament (MEP)). Both acknowledged their commitment and desire to conduct animal-free chemical safety assessment. Mrs Metz also recognised the effort needed to implement the roadmap and the requirement for better coordination and cross-sector approaches to achieve this goal. Further, chemicals legislation should increasingly reflect the value of non-animal methods.

The purpose of this workshop report is not to provide detailed minutes of the workshop, but rather to bring together the main themes from the presentations and discussion. For a detailed account of the workshop, the EC has published all slides and videos of the presentations from the workshop, which can be found at https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/events/commission-roadmap-phasing-out-animal-testing-chemical-safety-assessments-2023-12-11_en and a report at <http://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/e350d987-3820-11ef-b441-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-332073654>.

1.2. Definitions

Within the workshop, there was a divergence of opinions with regard to the exact definition of the terms “Non-Animal Methods” or animal-free methods, as well as a distinction between that and “New

Approach Methodologies” (NAMs) as some participants considered the latter term may include animal testing. Nevertheless, there was a consensus among participants that future toxicity testing should transition from establishing reference doses for hazard/risk assessment based on observed adverse effects to determining them from molecular-level changes. These changes are indicative of the toxicological mode of action and potential adverse outcomes. The goal of the roadmap discussed at the workshop is the transition to a regulatory system based on non-animal methods. For an interim period, NAMs-enhanced *in vivo* studies might be useful to reduce or refine animal testing. There was no agreement in the workshop on the definition of NAMs or their implementation as non-animal testing methods. The following summarises many of the proposed methods: non-animal methods were considered in a broad sense to include *in silico*, *in chemico* and *in vitro* approaches, Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs) and Defined Approaches (DAs) or non-animal omics approaches.

1.3. Context of the workshop

The workshop was held in response from the EC to the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) “*Save cruelty-free cosmetics – Commit to a Europe without animal testing*” which gained over one million statements of support (ECI, 2023). The response from the European Commission of July 25, 2023 to the ECI states the commitment to transform and modernise chemicals' legislation through the implementation of a roadmap towards animal-free chemical safety assessment (EC, 2023a). To support this, the European Commission committed to create the roadmap towards animal-free chemical safety assessment and to hold two workshops to present progress towards the roadmap, in the second halves of 2023 and 2024. The first of these workshops in December 2023, of which this document is the report, was intended to lay the

foundations for the roadmap in terms of gaining knowledge on the potential milestones and steps to achieve them.

The workshop was attended by representatives of multiple stakeholder groups who contributed by podium presentations, panel discussions or via questions and comments to the plenary sessions (both in person and on-line). Several organisations were represented, including the European Commission, agencies such as the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), and the European Medicines Agency (EMA), along with animal welfare NGOs, the European Partnership for Alternative Approaches to Animal Testing (EPAA), PARC, industry groups, academia, and others. Representatives of PARC Task 2.2 (“knowledge management and uptake into policy”) (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023) organised the afternoon discussion sessions on the second day of the workshop.

1.4. Presentations made at the workshop

Over the two days, the workshop was organised into five sessions with presentations and subsequent panel discussions, followed by two open discussion sessions. In addition to the introductory presentations, there were 25 platform presentations from stakeholders including regulatory agencies, scientific committees, NGOs, industry, academic and international projects, amongst others. In addition, there were three panel discussions with the aim to encourage active audience participation and input and questions and comments were collected from the on-line audience.

The full agenda, including details of speakers and panel discussion participants is provided at: <https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/presentations-workshop-commission-roadmap-towards-phasing-out-animal-testing-chemical-safety.en>.

This report does not intend to provide a full summary of the presentations (which can be viewed in the link above), but intends to briefly introduce the EC’s Roadmap Towards Phasing out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments to summarise the main discussion points and to illustrate the divergence of opinions from the stakeholders.

2. Purpose of a roadmap towards phasing out animal testing for chemical safety assessments

The planned roadmap is intended to be a policy document from the EC that will “outline milestones and specific actions” and address all “relevant pieces of EU chemical legislation (e.g., Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) Regulation, Biocidal Product Regulation, Plant Protection Products Regulation and human and veterinary medicines)”. Another piece of legislation in scope of the Roadmap is the Regulation on Classification, Labelling, and Packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures. The roadmap will not cover animal use for research e.g., bio-medical research.

The roadmap intends to analyse and to describe the necessary steps to replace animal testing in pieces of legislation that currently require animal testing for chemical safety assessments. The roadmap will outline the path to expand and accelerate the development, validation and implementation of non-animal methods as well as means to facilitate their uptake across legislations. A communication from the EC on the ECI (EC, 2023a) stated that the Roadmap will include and build on the elements summarised below to support the transition towards chemical safety assessments based on non-animal testing.

- Replacing animal testing: to analyse for each (eco-)toxicological endpoint the options to replace animal testing, identify gaps that have to be closed and development needs.
- Joining forces - stakeholder involvement: to communicate e.g., with workshops, the report being based on the first such workshop with a second planned in the second half of 2024.
- Strengthen collaboration of agencies and expert committees: an EC Proposal “Streamlining EU scientific and technical work on

chemicals through the EU agencies” (EC, 2023b) to strengthen collaboration of agencies and expert committees to accelerate the transfer of available scientific expertise to legislation. An analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the current landscape of agencies, committees and working groups that provide advice on non-animal methods. Exploration of opportunities for a stronger collaboration and analyse possibilities to accelerate the transfer of available scientific expertise to legislation.

- Advisory scientific committee on non-animal methods: analysis of the need/feasibility of an expert scientific committee to provide advice on the development of non-animal approaches and their use in the regulatory context.
- Acceptance of methods: Analysis of the ways to accelerate the acceptance of new non-animal methods, while taking into account the importance of mutual acceptance of data across different jurisdictions This includes the need to increase validation but also the regulatory uptake of non-animal methods.
- International dimension: Outreach to non-EU partner countries and multilateral organisations to foster the development and acceptance of non-animal testing methods for regulatory purposes. Consideration of the UN Globally Harmonised System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals.
- Agencies involvement in international forums: Analysis of how to increase the agencies’ visibility and impact in international forums, such as Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), World Health Organization (WHO), Accelerating the Pace of Chemical Risk Assessment (APCRA) etc.
- Improve availability and accessibility of information: A proposal on a regulation on chemicals data that will improve accessibility to information on chemicals. Analysis of how to facilitate access to information such as upcoming events, calls, guidance.
- Outreach to scientific community and stakeholders: Increase outreach to stakeholders and the scientific community, with support of its agencies, to receive the necessary input on how to replace animal testing with non-animal approaches, e.g., via the organisation of workshops, the annual conference under the umbrella of EPAA or contributions to conferences.

Feedback was sought on these elements and is summarised in Fig. 1 and detailed in Sections 3 and 4. Further, the workshop considered advances in scientific approaches and methodologies with regard to chemical safety assessment in order to help prepare a roadmap for this specific area. These included developments in *in vitro* and other non-animal methods as well as tiered strategies for their implementation. Existing initiatives towards the general aim of animal-free chemical safety assessment were presented. These include those from the United States (US) to improve the regulatory acceptance of non-animal methods (ICCVAM, 2018) and from EFSA for the use of NAMs (Escher et al., 2022).

3. Stakeholders’ perspectives on requirements for the roadmap

The workshop heard a range of opinions relating to the need for a roadmap and the ultimate aim of achieving animal-free chemical safety assessment. The workshop aimed to gather comments, feedback, and suggestions from a wide range of stakeholders rather than to reach agreement or consensus. These contributions are summarised below which act as support for, and a basis for part of, the roadmap.

3.1. Past and on-going activities that May inform the roadmap

The development of the roadmap was seen as a collective effort requiring buy-in by all stakeholders. Stakeholders reported activities that could inform and support the development of the roadmap and, more specifically, the implementation of non-animal methods for animal-free chemical safety assessment. Some of these activities are

Fig. 1. Summary of the feedback received in the roadmap with details in Sections 3 and 4.

summarised in this section or referred to in subsequent sections.

ECHA is proactively promoting the increased use of non-animal methods and recognises the need to agree on critical elements to be addressed to enable a transition to an animal-free regulatory system. ECHA reported on the main outcomes from a Workshop on new approach methodologies organised (31 May – June 1, 2023) to discuss the critical needs to move towards an animal free regulatory system for industrial chemicals. The workshop brought together perspectives from different stakeholders and explored opportunities to increase the use of new approach methodologies in the short- and long-term. The ECHA workshop demonstrated a strong commitment from all stakeholders but with different expectations on how to progress and how rapidly progress can be made (ECHA, 2023b). ECHA also published in June 2023 a document on the “Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge” (ECHA, 2023a), with the document to be updated annually. Four key areas are foreseen, namely to provide protection against the most harmful chemicals, to address chemical pollution in the environment, the shift away from animal testing and to improve availability of chemical data. Three steps were identified to move away from animal testing using new approach methodologies: the identification of critical needs, application of existing new approach methodologies and re-design of the overall safety assessment process (use of information about chemical activity and exposure to manage risk).

EFSA also supports the use of NAMs in risk assessment. EFSA provided several examples of the use of NAMs to fill data gaps where traditional data are not available, to complement existing data as part of a Weight-of-Evidence (WoE) approach and to support the phasing out of testing on animals. However, validated and accepted NAMs are not currently available for key elements of the existing regulatory requirements (in common with other regulations). In 2022, EFSA published a Roadmap for action on the use of NAMs in regulatory hazard and risk characterisations of chemicals in food and feed, also an area promoted in the EFSA Strategy 2027 (Escher et al., 2022).

EMA prioritises the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) in evaluating pharmaceuticals, biologically-based medicines, and

vaccines. EMA considers endorsement and acceptance as the most important criteria for NAMs. A Working Party on the 3Rs (3RsWP) has also been instigated by EMA.¹ This has high level strategic goals to implement 3Rs into the authorisation of medicinal products. In addition, EMA has a platform for information sharing and facilitating interactions between experts in the non-clinical field, including NAMs; this is termed the Non-Clinical and New Approach Methodologies European Specialised Expert Community. More information is available from: <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/committees/working-parties-other-groups/chmp/non-clinical-new-approach-methodologies-european-specialised-expert-community>.

CEFIC, representing the European Chemical Industry, is committed to the development and regulatory acceptance of animal-free methodologies for the advancement of chemical safety. In alignment with change management approaches, CEFIC proposed to consider three core elements: (1) the planning, discussion and agreement on objectives, deliverables and timelines; (2) the design and implementation at global level of high-quality standards; and (3) the continuous verification and calibration of expectations throughout the change management process. Important points for each of these core elements were flagged.

- More flexibility in chemical regulation and the use of New Approach Methods where already possible, e.g. for simple endpoints or read-across was identified as a measure that could be implemented in the short term. The long-term vision on the other hand would require a paradigm shift, mainly for EU CLP and United Nations Globally Harmonized System (UN GHS) classification rules away from today’s apical endpoints towards a holistic approach to chemical safety.
- Internationally harmonised standards for methods becoming Standard Information Requirements (SIRs) under REACH and the respect of OECD Mutual Acceptance of Data (MAD) rules were identified as key success factors for the implementation of new approaches. Due care should be taken during the standardisation and validation processes to the needs and limitations for difficult to test substances.

¹ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/committees/working-parties-other-groups/chmp/3rs-working-party>.

- These tasks will require adequate resourcing and hence only be enabled by appropriate partnerships and resource sharing. The creation of safe spaces and knowledge hubs should further improve mutual confidence in how NAMs are applied (e.g. on case studies).

Humane Society International (HSI) promoted the open, transparent and inclusive building of the roadmap. In particular, the inclusion of defined milestones within a roadmap, focussing on the removal of the requirement in chemicals legislation for redundant and/or duplicative tests, the full phasing out of animal testing in chemical safety assessment and the need to address intersectional inconsistencies in regulation. Disruption of existing regulatory frameworks as a reality of the ultimate goal of the Roadmap was mentioned by HSI, encouraging the audience to embrace disruption as a vector for positive change. HSI emphasised the need to establish mechanisms to monitor progress, a commitment to transforming validation and alignment on common language on non-animal methods and health protection goals. The creation of safe spaces was also promoted by HSI.

Contributions were also received from two EU-funded projects. PARC includes work packages on hazard assessment and innovation in regulatory risk assessment. It can provide toxicity data, innovative NAMs – including those with a high level of regulatory readiness, IATAs and develops concepts and criteria for NAMs for regulatory use. It has also started to develop a roadmap towards establishing Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) as the default approach to risk assessment in EU chemicals legislation, which in the future will be continued in close collaboration with the work on the EU Commission's roadmap. Furthermore, it has launched an online knowledge management and community platform (PARCopedia, <https://parcopedia.eu>) for chemical risk assessment professionals in, as well as outside of, PARC. The Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies (ASPIIS) Cluster is initiating the development of the Alternative Safety Profiling Approach (ASPA) framework which will provide a tiered strategy for the implementation of NAMs. In addition, there will be considerable learnings available from EPAA's "NAM Designathon 2023" challenge for human systemic toxicity. The Designathon seeks to identify classification systems capable of categorising chemicals based on the intrinsic toxicodynamic and toxicokinetic properties. The preliminary results were released in a workshop in March 2024. More details on the Designathon, including updates on results, are available from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/calls-expression-interest/epaa-launches-designathon-human-systemic-toxicity_en.

4. Recommendations for the roadmap

This section compiles and summarises the discussion points made in the workshop that were considered by participants as relevant for the roadmap. Many workshop participants stated that the roadmap needs well-defined milestones with a robust plan to achieve them. Consistent with the purpose of the workshop, participants expressed a broad range of opinions. This summary attempts to provide some insight into the range of opinions, noting that consensus was not sought or achieved and there was no common agreement on any recommendation. As appropriate, the summary in this section is organised with regard to human health and environmental effects representing individual contributions to the workshop, although it is noted that some approaches may be common to both.

4.1. Mapping and gap analysis of needs and available NAMs

Several participants considered that there is a need for a co-ordinated approach to identify the existing alternatives to animal testing. As part of this, a fundamental requirement is to understand and document the state of the science with regard to alternatives to animal tests. As such, it is crucial to map the current data requirements for chemical safety

assessment in different product or substance-specific regulatory frameworks, i.e., to map the animal-based apical data generated for regulatory endpoints that are currently required or can be triggered by chemical legislation. In addition, a defined list of protection goals and regulatory needs is fundamental for advancing the transition away from animal testing. The information should be sufficient for hazard identification and characterisation and enable exposure and risk assessment, where required. The research and development needs for animal-free chemical safety assessment should be defined including a gap analysis to determine what is missing and how to prioritise further method development.

The consideration of needs can be supplemented by mapping which non-animal NAMs and other approaches are currently available. This analysis will enable the identification of where animal-free methods are suitably developed for use, as well as the limitations, gaps and needs for development or acceptance of new methodologies. Animal-free NAMs should be mapped to understand the information they provide and, if necessary, matched with the endpoints from animal-based studies. The non-animal approaches need to be assessed against the protection goals established through current and updated or future regulation. The level of confidence provided by current and future non-animal approaches should be assessed.

Considering the mapping process, it is important to create a global perspective on the needs and possibilities of animal-free chemical safety assessment. The purpose of the mapping is to provide opportunities to facilitate exchange and harmonisation amongst jurisdictions and industrial sectors. The possibility to foster cooperation with ongoing activities on research projects, as well as ensuring the crossover between human health and environment, should be encouraged. As noted previously, a broad range of opinions were received on measures that could be implemented in the short to longer term.

4.2. Regulatory decisions on new types of data

Participants emphasised opportunities and needs to progressively adapt legislative frameworks to account for the progress and possibilities of NAMs. This can take account of scientific principles as well as societal needs and expectations expressed in the ECI. The modernisation of legislation should take advantage of the opportunity to allow for international harmonisation to assist with the global replacement of animals in chemical safety assessment. The adaptation of legislation and/or regulatory guidance should allow for the phasing out of redundant information requirements or tests i.e., those that do not provide any new information; or animal tests for which validated and accepted non-animal methods are available.

Some participants mentioned that legislation or regulatory guidance may need to be significantly changed to ensure protection goals are met with information based on animal-free testing only. Regulatory frameworks must be increasingly flexible to accommodate improved science, rather than trying to change science to fit into current regulatory frameworks.

To understand how changes could be achieved, there was discussion of various pieces of legislation. Classification and Labelling (C&L) relates to all chemicals on the market. It crosses all industrial sectors (e.g. plant protection products, biocides, cosmetics, human and veterinary medicines, industrial chemicals etc). Data to make C&L decisions are obtained from the information required under various pieces of legislation e.g., REACH. The GHS for C&L is implemented in the EU through the CLP regulation. To fully cover the spectrum of endpoints in the CLP Regulation requires knowledge of local and systemic health effects across a range of toxicities including endocrine disruption. The possibility of developing NAMs to be used for classification of systemic toxicity is explored in initiatives such as RISK-HUNT3R² and PARC Work

² <https://www.risk-hunt3r.eu/>.

Package 5.³ Within the workshop, there were different understandings amongst the stakeholders (e.g., EC, Agencies, Member States, industry, NGOs) about whether or not sufficiently reliable NAMs are available for hazard classification (CLP) and/or for risk assessment and about the degree of confidence in them that is needed. There were also differences of opinion with regard to NAMs such as read-across, grouping, omics etc which may reduce, rather than fully replace testing.

4.3. Validation of NAMs

Several prerequisites for the use of NAM data to replace animal tests were identified in the workshop. These include the validation of methods, models and tools. Following from this is the need for improved understanding of the criteria required for allowing and improving regulatory acceptance of NAMs. In addition, terms such as “valid” and “validated” may be interpreted differently depending on the context, use and sector to which they are applied. The process of validation is currently seen as a precondition, but in practice also a challenge and a bottleneck, to the regulatory acceptance of NAMs. There was a discussion regarding the need to update the current process for validating/demonstrating the scientific robustness and reliability, and relevance for context of uses (e.g., regulatory decision-making) of the NAMs. The following summarises a range of opinions on the current situation, needs and some proposals to update the validation process.

Validation, in the context of making NAMs acceptable for regulatory use, is a process that is anchored in scientific principles and seeks to demonstrate the reliability and relevance of a new method, such as a NAM, for a particular purpose. It also serves to build trust and confidence within a regulatory context of use. Validation paves the way for regulatory acceptance which is needed to assure that the data from the validated method can be used in regulatory decision making.

NAMs must be shown to be ready for regulatory use, which may include having an OECD Test Guideline (TG). However, tests may be considered valid without undergoing formal validation, with considerations ongoing to validate tests in the future without undergoing all steps of the formal international validation process. A guiding principle is that NAMs will be expected to be fit for a specific purpose, for instance to be able to inform on hazard and risk. Adoption of NAMs in OECD TGs is currently a prerequisite for global MAD. OECD-accepted methods, carried out under Good Laboratory Practice (GLP), are the accepted norm under most of today’s regulatory areas. These standards warrant reliability and reusability, allowing for mutual acceptance across legislations and geographic regions. Data from OECD-accepted methods hence provide regulatory predictability and demonstration of compliance.

The current system for validation and acceptance of new methods for hazard and safety assessments is based on OECD Guidance Document 34 (GD 34) (OECD, 2005). GD 34 is perceived by many as being outdated with regard to progress made in toxicology, and the new technologies and scientific approaches on which NAMs are based. In addition, the validation process itself, also covered in GD 34 is too slow and cause of bottlenecks. Though the principles of validation as defined by GD 34 are universal, the overall context has changed and a revision deemed appropriate.

Key new concepts in validation of NAMs are described in van der Zalm et al. (2022) as well as in a more recent proposal from the Inter-agency Coordinating Committee on the Validation of Alternative Methods (ICCVAM, 2023). These documents also describe the key concepts to consider during the development and implementation of flexible, efficient, and fit-for-purpose validation processes of NAMs.

The need for a paradigm shift in how validation is performed was acknowledged within the workshop though no formal agreement was achieved on details of how. It was discussed that such a shift requires an

understanding of the needs for validation as well as an evolution of thinking (Hilton et al., 2023). Ranging from initial screening and priority setting, to full hazard assessment and C&L use of a NAM, validation may become adaptable to different needs. The full set of use case scenarios would need to be defined for the validation process.

Key questions can already be defined to accelerate the validation process. Key questions were derived considering the various full steps of validation to acceptance (e.g., van der Zalm et al., 2022) and include some open questions.

- What is the degree of reproducibility (intra- and inter-laboratory) that is required for the NAM?
- What are the key requirements in terms of toxicological validation, how and which reference data should comparison be made with and how many reference substances are needed?
- How is the NAM to be used in decision making and what additional evidence is required to make such a decision?
- What are the key drivers for regulators to be able to accept a decision based on hazard data?

In addition, NAMs may have to be used in concert and therefore these validation questions also apply to IATAs or DAs. As stated above, the principles and process of validation is presented in OECD GD 34. As part of the activity of updating GD 34, the following have been identified as the top priorities.

- i) Validation of DAs and their building blocks.
- ii) Inclusion of more practical guidance on validation, such as chemicals selection, data integrity, quality assurance, study design.
- iii) Defining the concept of technical validation.
- iv) Assessment of relevance beyond accuracy to predict animal data.
- v) Validation of new technologies such as Organ-on-a-Chip (OoC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) assisted methods.
- vi) Revision of the process to assess reproducibility and transferability.
- vii) Evolution of performance standards.

Future work on validation should consider the relevance of the NAM, with a particular emphasis on how to benchmark new methods if *in vivo* animal data are not available or not appropriate. In such cases, relevance may focus on mechanistic relevance to the endpoint of interest, and concordance with other NAMs for the same property. The validation of certain new technologies is not addressed in the current OECD GD 34. As such, there will be a requirement for well-designed transfer studies between labs to demonstrate portability as well as appropriate training in the new method. There will also be a need to evolve and apply performance standards that can be used to demonstrate equivalency of information to other methods for the same endpoint. These aspects would characterise the components of the test method, consider outputs to reference chemicals, and aim to demonstrate reproducibility and predictive capacity.

4.4. Regulatory acceptance of NAMs

A number of opinions on regulatory acceptance of NAMs were received at the workshop, with validation seen as a key step. To achieve regulatory acceptance of NAMs, in addition to being a validated method or approach, there is a need to gain an understanding of the acceptable level of uncertainty in using the NAM for a particular purpose and context. Acceptable uncertainty may be compared with what is currently acceptable Evaluating the protection level provided by animal tests—considered acceptable by authorities— could involve comparing results to human and epidemiological data when available and could include assessing their reproducibility, accuracy, and reliability. This would establish the uncertainty baseline that non-animal methods must

³ <https://www.eu-parc.eu/deliverables>.

meet or exceed to be deemed acceptable. Therefore, it is important to define the milestone(s) for achieving faster regulatory acceptance in the roadmap.

There was an appreciation that validation and regulatory acceptance need harmonisation between different initiatives, sectors, regulations and geographic regions. The experiences in the US from developing a roadmap to improve the regulatory acceptance of NAMs were also described. The ICCVAM strategic roadmap is a resource to help guide the development of new methods applying flexible approaches to establish confidence in new methods (ICCVAM, 2018). It aims to encourage the adoption of new methods by U.S. Federal Agencies and regulated industries and recognises that advances in science and technology have not yet been properly leveraged to predict adverse human health effects. The PARC Project is developing “NGRAroute”, which is a roadmap for making EU chemicals legislation NGRA-ready. The vision for NGRA-route is to provide a concrete and applicable roadmap proposal by April 2025 for implementing NGRA, in the long-term, as the default approach to chemical risk assessment in EU chemicals legislation. This will, *inter alia*, build on the “ASPA”, the “ASPIS-initiated Safety Profiling Algorithm”, an NGRA framework currently developed under the ASPIS cluster.⁴ The scope is intended to include all European chemicals legislation with a risk assessment component (i.e., hazard and/or exposure and/or risk), for human health and environmental risk assessment. Ten guiding principles for an NGRA framework to be established in EU chemicals legislation have been drafted and were discussed in detail at the workshop, along with possible work streams under the roadmap and their specific tasks. Collaboration on NGRAroute will be closely coordinated with partners from other work packages in PARC, as well as other ongoing EU projects, including stakeholders within, and outside of, the Partnership.

4.5. Consideration of exposure and role of toxicokinetics (TK)

Understanding exposure is a significant part of the determination of chemical safety assessment for human health and the environment for many substances. A number of opinions on how exposure could be integrated into non-animal chemical safety assessment were presented at the workshop, some of which are presented below, although no attempt was necessarily made to reach agreement or consensus on any particular approach.

Assessment of exposure is fundamental to the application of NGRA and new approach methodologies therein. It will require consideration of both internal and external exposure estimates. Approaches such as the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) are applied in the safety assessment of impurities (e.g., in food) and low concentrations of ingredients (e.g., in cosmetics). The concept could be extended to the development of an internal TTC i.e., a threshold set on extrapolating internal concentrations for the derivation of a Point of Departure (PoD) in human health assessment.

With regard to understanding and utilising exposure, there is a need to learn from best practices, with considerable experience available in some sectors e.g., pharmaceuticals, cosmetics. In general, there is a necessity to reassess exposure estimates and models, e.g., for occupational and consumer exposure to chemicals. Several participants pointed towards short-term measures that could lead to an imminent reduction of animal testing and uncertainty in human and environmental protection. It is based on the adoption of exposure-driven decisions for higher tier testing requirements and the improvement of exposure knowledge in case confidence in this knowledge is lacking. Policy changes towards such an increased exposure driven management of risk posed by chemicals would enable resources to be re-invested in faster development and validation of new experimental methods.

It is further crucial to understand real exposure patterns for instance

to incentivise use of monitoring and modelling to improve exposure assessment. The achieved reduction of the uncertainties could than facilitate acceptance for exposure-based adaptation (EBA) and waiving of animal tests, an approach that has the potential to drastically reduce the need for animals while heading towards the long-term goal of full replacement of animal tests. More approaches for waiving the (regulatory) requirements for animal test requirements were described which could be improved and developed further for exposure-based waiving should be further explored and implemented as EBA.

It is important to gain a better understanding of when sufficient confidence is attained for EBA opportunities. This could be achieved by combining different lines of evidence, but still would require guidance on how to structure the multiple lines of evidence into a WoE approach, agreement across stakeholders on the protection goals and the levels of confidence to be achieved. In common with human health, a better understanding of internal exposure of environmental species is also needed. Toxicokinetics (TK) models are helpful tools to enhance consideration of internal exposure and interpretation of *in vitro* data.

4.6. Mode and mechanism of action

With regard to systemic human health effects, several participants voiced their opinion that there will be no one-to-one replacement of a complex *in vivo* test with a single NAM. Mechanistic knowledge will create trust and confidence in the use of NAM data. Therefore, the use of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) should also be included in the roadmap. However, it is unlikely that there will be complete coverage of all (mechanistically-relevant) AOPs. Due to that, it was suggested to focus on covering intermediate effects shown to be of concern for adversity avoiding unnecessary overlap, to minimise the number of predicted effects. For such effects quantitative NAM readouts are preferred. One way in which this could potentially be achieved is through an improved linkage of biomarkers for tissue injury with mechanistic key events.

With regard to the application of AOPs there is a need to identify, using NAMs, intermediate key effects (KEs) leading to the adverse outcome, rather than assessing or predicting the adverse outcome itself. Realistically, a prediction of all effects detected in animal models and in humans to fit the current CLP-based chemical management framework will not be possible, at least in the short-term. To achieve a phaseout of animal testing, a shift in mindset and change in regulations is hence required towards improved but targeted mechanistic knowledge. Additionally, there is a requirement to establish consensus on the extent of coverage needed for various uses, along with the endpoints and exposure categories to be included. Regardless of the NAM methods utilised, demonstrating the ability to maintain, or improve on, current protection levels is essential.

4.7. Development of frameworks for data integration and decision making

A number of opinions were made with regard to data integration. Single NAMs in isolation are unlikely to provide sufficient information for hazard characterisation, especially for systemic toxicity. Therefore, there will be a need to utilise more than a single NAM, which implies the need for a battery of tests or framework to integrate the data and create an appropriate WoE. There is also a need to develop frameworks to apply NAM data for decision-making. Frameworks are likely to be based on tiered approaches and since multiple lines of evidence will need to be incorporated, these will need to be well defined and structured to allow for efficient (regulatory) decision-making. The integration of data should allow for the creation of links across methods, endpoints, and species/taxa.

Relevant AOPs will be key to the development of tiered testing strategies in the future. There is a short-term opportunity (as part of the mapping process) to identify useable frameworks and to structure existing NAMs into similar frameworks. The medium-term is likely to

⁴ <https://aspis-cluster.eu>.

benefit from new *in vitro* methods to replace existing *in vivo* tests as well as reduction in testing through more efficient screening and prioritisation. For environmental species and effects, the long term-aim is seen as the development of NAM-based Environmental Safety Assessment (ESA), specifically applying an IATA-based design, e.g. using PoDs from other taxa or *in silico* predictions. It is important to integrate different assays such as combining toxicity, bioaccumulation and TK and gaining a better understanding of internal concentrations. There is also a need to design the ESA requirements as part of other legislations that support wide environmental protection policies e.g., Water Framework Directive, biodiversity protection etc.

4.8. Data sharing and access – ensuring transparency and “safe spaces”

Some participants opined that there is a requirement to make more data from NAMs available for the purpose of the validation process for inspection by regulatory risk assessors. There is an opportunity and a need to enrich available databases of hazard information, for instance ECHA’s database on chemicals. Better access to data will help understand how NAMs function, thus streamlining their acceptance. By understanding the mechanisms behind adverse effects, we can design NAMs which address the shortcomings of animal tests - which often measure observable effects without fully understanding the process. The possibility to utilise data for pharmaceuticals as standards was highlighted. To improve the access to more NAM data, a common platform to share data is needed. It is relevant to mention in this context that the European Commission has proposed a legislative act to establish such a common data platform (EC, 2023c).

The concept of safe spaces was proposed. Safe spaces could facilitate free exchange of ideas, methodologies and data. They would allow an open, back-and-forth, dialogue to be conducted between industry and regulatory agencies normally not possible under strict timelines in regulatory processes. One aspect of the safe space concept could be to allow data on NAMs to be submitted simultaneously with data currently required for regulatory purposes, thus allowing for an assessment of the non-animal data without prejudice and/or regulatory consequence. It is recognised that this requires sufficient expertise within both industry and regulatory stakeholders to interpret and evaluate the data, as well as sufficient resources from regulators, hence would be difficult for all substances falling under REACH. An option proposed to facilitate the use of safe space could be to form interagency committees staffed by experts on NAMs.

4.9. Outreach and involvement of stakeholders

The crucial aspect of the full involvement of stakeholders in the implementation of NAMs was emphasised on several occasions during the workshop. The aim is to identify and integrate best practice, to highlight international partnerships and precedents from other international regulatory frameworks and to secure the involvement of stakeholders across sectors throughout the entire change management processes. There are many routes to achieve outreach and stakeholder involvement, these are summarised in this section drawing on evidence from all sessions and presentations.

Outreach is also crucial for transparency in the use of NAMs and to increase involvement and understanding between all stakeholders. In addition, this will also demonstrate the value of sharing knowledge, experience, data and methodologies. International partnerships and networks are seen as valuable to share information and knowledge. Examples of partnerships include PARC, ASPIS Cluster and APCRA – all of which are on-going. Case studies were seen as a very valuable tool to demonstrate and increase confidence in the use of NAMs in a regulatory context. Such explorative tools, along with sharing of common guidance on the application of NAMs will allow for their greater understanding and uptake. Dissemination events and organisation of workshops on how to progress on the roadmap and the proposed measures will be

required, for instance with the collaboration of the EPAA.

Some participants emphasised the importance to consider socio-technical barriers to the uptake of new methodologies and in safety assessment, both from the angle of industry and regulators. Rules and standards for chemical safety assessment require change in the law and guidance. Infrastructure as well as processes may need to be updated in both, authorities and industry, calling for additional investments. To overcome the barriers there is a need for NAMs to demonstrate their relevance, reliability and their fitness-for-purpose make regulatory decisions. The clear value of NAMs must be demonstrated with regard to ethics, time and cost comparison, the use of better science and legal considerations. Transition theory is one method that may be applied to clear these socio-technical barriers (Abarkan et al., 2022).

Some participants emphasised the need for capacity building across all stakeholders. Training and education in all aspects of NAMs, from university courses to professional qualification, are essential. Participants mentioned that training is required specifically for the regulators in Governmental Agencies and a need to provide training to the trainers themselves. This process would require appropriate funding, as well as an appreciation of which topics to include in the training.

4.10. Other suggestions of measures made during the workshop for implementation in the short and medium term

A variety of non-test approaches and *in silico* models were referred to in the workshop. These ranged from read-across, to the use of (quantitative) structure-activity relationships ((Q)SARs), machine learning, quantitative AOPs (qAOPs), and physiologically-based kinetic (PBK) exposure modelling. Useable *in silico* approaches and their applications should be identified. For complex endpoints such as systemic toxicity, it is highly probable that individual *in silico* models on their own will not be acceptable in the replacement of existing animal testing requirements (in the short or medium term) but may be combined with other approaches and could support decision forming in an overall WoE. Read-across is seen as a plausible approach for addressing complex endpoints under the current safety paradigm, specifically where NAM data can complement the various lines of evidence forming the WoE.

4.11. Other needs

Other opinions relating to the roadmap were made, which include.

- Comparison of *in vitro* data with human data is essential to increase confidence in NAMs.
- Funding is required for development and validation of NAMs, in addition to education.
- More work is needed on complex mixtures and substances that are difficult to test. Examples stated include unknown or variable composition, complex reaction products or of biological materials (UVCBs) such as hydrocarbons, fragrances; surfactants, ionisable chemicals and other substances.
- Regulatory predictability for the use of NAMs with regard to compliance with regulatory requirements should be assessed.
- In addition to the current expert groups, there may be a need to create more expert groups to facilitate the use of NAMs.

5. Conclusions

A “Roadmap Towards Phasing Out Animal Testing for Chemical Safety Assessments” is being prepared by the European Commission, as a response to the ECI “Save cruelty-free cosmetics – Commit to a Europe without animal testing”. The workshop introduced the purpose of the roadmap as being a policy document that will outline milestones and specific actions and address all relevant pieces of chemical legislation towards achieving animal-free chemical safety assessments. The possible content of a roadmap was discussed by the participants of the

workshop, who provided extensive input into its requirements. The contributions (in terms of presentations) from the workshop participants covered many topics, including expectations from an animal-free assessment approach, mode and mechanism of action, consideration of exposure and toxicokinetics, validation and regulatory acceptance, socio-technical barriers to change. They highlighted the aim to use the best science to achieve the aim of phasing out animal testing. With regard to this, there was a broad range of opinions on many topics, especially related, but not limited to, timelines, requirements to make a safety assessment, terminology and validation of NAMs as well as the priorities and milestones for the roadmap. Overall, the insight from participants on the wide range of relevant issues gave valuable input to the development of the roadmap, however it also demonstrated the challenges inherent to phasing out animal testing. Whilst there were a variety of opinions, there was a general agreement that ultimately phasing out animal testing will require a new way of assessing chemicals. Participants emphasised that with maturing science it is time of moving towards phasing out animal testing. In conclusion, participants were committed to further collaborate on developing the roadmap.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mark T.D. Cronin: Writing – original draft. **Elisabet Berggren:** Writing – review & editing. **Sofia Camorani:** Writing – review & editing. **Christian Desaintes:** Writing – review & editing. **Marco Fabbri:** Writing – review & editing. **Julia Fabrega:** Writing – review & editing. **Matthias Herzler:** Writing – review & editing. **Jay D.E. Ingram:** Writing – review & editing. **Katia Lacasse:** Writing – review & editing. **Susanna Louhimies:** Writing – review & editing. **Gavin Maxwell:** Writing – review & editing. **Katrin Schutte:** Writing – review & editing. **Tomasz Sobanski:** Writing – review & editing. **Georg Streck:** Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Terron:** Writing – review & editing. **Andrew P. Worth:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

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